
Discourses, Structures and Analysis: What Practices? , in Which Contexts?

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"Social research is a necessary and impossible task. Necessary since the vision (semantic) and the handling (pragmatic), 'rational', of the social order demand it. Social research is factually and potentially impossible: Potentially impossible since the social order only works if it is inconsistent; Rightly, since it is paradoxical (the empirical and theoretical proof are self-referent sentences, the empirical proof needs to measure the society with social instruments, the theoretical proof needs the language or thinking the thought)." (Ibañez, Jesús. 1988)

"The social order is the order of saying." (Ibañez, Jesús. 1990)

It is not easy to outline the "position" from which I want to delimitate the lines of debate. It is an additional difficulty because it necessarily implies to undressing in public and, consequently, the provocation of an embarrassing situation. If sincerity has some value in the situation we are defining, then I am obliged to go further in the description of this position. If this is not meant as an unnecessary psychologization, let's go with the positionment.

I am talking from a position of lecturer/researcher, immersed in the Spanish university system, with all the implications of this fact. I am 'impelled' to research; I analyse discourses, and I am doing it with a particular analytical tool: discourse analysis (DA). I am trying to think about the notion of discourse I use, and about the kind of practices, definable as DA, I use. But...

What am I trying to achieve by acting like this? Is it only the 'obligation' of following the normative that could be applied to any researcher in Spain? Is it the shameful passion of a voyeur, of seeing and scrutinizing everything that effects the people I am living with? Is it, on the other hand, a more shameful motivation consisting of the achievement of recognition from my professional colleagues? Is it, finally, a more 'rational' task? Answering the first questions will definitely locate us in an excessive psychologist framework, too excessive to be 'acceptable' in this respectable meeting. I will try, though, to answer only publicly the last one publicly.

Although the answer is not easy, what do I expect when I am doing what I use to? To explain? , To describe? , To understand? , To interpret? All these are forms of generating knowledge and making it possible. Nevertheless, the implication of a task like "Critical Social Psychology" makes some forms inadequate; this is one of the reasons we are here together. I will try to clarify an answer in this "position paper", and I will do it through a problematization of the notion of discourse and the notion of DA.

INTRODUCTION

There is no doubt that, in the last few years, we can talk about a new 'atmosphere' in Social Psychology. Some dissident positions are heard with more attention than some years ago. This is particularly appreciable in the empirical analysis of social processes where, for example, there is a progressive abandon of experimental and correlational methods. This is why some people are beginning to talk about the gradual majority presence of what we could label as "discursive" ("palabrerros" in a more castillian pejorative way).

Of course, this has its advantages for those who work in the same direction. I am deliberately going to keep this orientation vague, calling it by convention "discursivist". These advantages are: progressive disciplinary and academic recognition, attention to this specialty by journals, specific collections in major publishers, etc.

Nevertheless, we should not be fooled. If we can identify these lines of change it does not necessarily mean that they are homogeneously manifested in all contexts. Of the huge number of social psychologists in the Spanish State¹ there are few who work in a "discursive" direction. There are only: a group in the Complutense University of Madrid, a few people distributed among different universities, and the group that welcomes you today that can be identified with this orientation.

To use a metaphor, when you raise your head you receive many indiscriminate blows. This is specially evident in the academic context of the Spanish State. I would say this happens because they take aim without seeing the whole target. From the position of the hegemony of Social Psychology they attribute a series of inaccurate, even erroneous, traits based on a series of stereotypes such as lack of objectivity, triviality, relativism, etc.

In a variety of occasions I proposed discussions around these new forms with different results depending on the situations. It is difficult to deny that my intentions have been more offensive than defensive; but, I have to say, restrained intentions (otherwise, I would be less than polite to those who do not assume my position). Of course, this is not true at this meeting as, from the beginning, we are on the same wavelength on many principles. Nevertheless, unanimity is not absolute and I am not sure it would be desirable. The discrepancies will be many and may even be more than the points of agreement.

¹ The terms *Spanish* and *Spaniard* are used very little in Catalonia because they refer to the idea of the Nation-State; which is not acknowledged by an important number of people in Catalonia. The existence of unrecognized deep national feelings in Catalonia, the Basque Country, and Galicia provoke a great number of symbolic and material conflicts. These conflicts are reflected in the use of some terms that allow the reflection of this reality and escape from the reality it pretends to impose. We therefore use "*Spanish State*" (and not "*Spain*") and "*Castilian*" (and not "*Spanish*").

CONCEPTIONS OF DISCOURSE/S

Discourse is such a polysemic term that saying "I am going to make the notion of discourse problematic" is equivalent at saying nothing at all. I am therefore going to limit this exposition to the consideration of the most common notions of discourse that appear in the disciplinary framework of Social Psychology, considering its characteristic disciplinary or theoretical traditions, and avoiding the consideration of other notions of discourse outside these limits. In particular, I am going to consider those notions of discourse grounded in these three traditions: First, the linguistic philosophy associated with the Oxford school; secondly, the work of Michael Foucault; and finally, the French pragmatics. This simplification obeys to the need of making an equivalent interpretation of the terms possible in the discussion. Therefore, I am not going to present an exhaustive revision but a quick one.

Depending on the notion of discourse we work with, DA will mean different things. Therefore, if we want to avoid a 'de facto' definition like 'discourse is what analysts analyze' (which is not unusual) the delimitation of this term appears to be a pertinent task.

Without assuming a complete classification, this small typology summarizes the most usual conceptions of discourse; as they are expressed in common analytical practices in Social psychology; at least:

- a. Any statement or set of statements produced by a speaker.
- b. A set of statements that construct an object.
- c. Set of statements produced in a context of interaction where their capacity of action on the other person is relevant (speaking subject, moment and space, . . .)
- d. Set of statements in a conversational (therefore normative) context
- e. Set of constrictions that explain the production of a set of statements from a social or ideological position (feminist or marxist discourse for example).
- f. Set of statements by which can be defined a set of conditions of production.

The last conception can be clearly recognized inside the French school of discourse analysis. This movement has profound influences from Foucault's work and it considers the distinction between enunciation and discourse. Enunciation is the succession of sentences between two semantic blanks. Discourse is the statement considered from the perspective of the conditioning discursive device. The term statement is regarded in this context as a result, as something with a certain amount of memory.

Among these conceptions of discourse the more appropriate, from my point of view, is the last one. This does not mean the discredit of other common conceptions in Social Psychology. They are not, in fact, incompatible but superimposed. One first superimposition consists in the different levels of analysis, from the pure interindividual to the clearly structural. They reproduce the sequence from the typical naive definition to the consequences of Speech Acts Theory; going through the ethnomethodological tradition (close to conversational analysis) or the most common from a post-structuralist legacy. They are not mutually exclusive; we use to find aspects from all of them in notions or in practices of discourse analysis (we uncover aspects from them in the work, for example, of Antaki, Parker, Potter and Wetherell and Walkerdine).

If I prefer the last one it is because from my perspective it allows three indispensable operations: the differentiation between text and discourse, the distinction announcer-enunciator and the operationalization of the corpus.

a. The Text

The first problem we find once we define discourse is the pattern of the characteristics of their texts. The main difference is in the consideration of the text as a set of transcribed statements, independently from its origin, or as a wider specification of what texts really are. In other words: Is any text a discourse?

From our position the answer is **no**. For a text to be a discourse a set of conditions should be considered. First, those statements produced in the institutional arena which restrict the enunciation can be considered discourses; in other words, those statements enunciated from defined positions, inside an inter-discursive context and revealing historical, social and intellectual conditions.

Any set of statements does not necessarily fulfill these conditions: only those who carry a specific value for a collective, who imply a clear position in a discursive network. In Foucaultian terms, text is not considered by itself, but as a part of a recognized institution that "defines for a specific social, economical, geographical or linguistic area the conditions for the fulfillment of the enunciative function". The relationships with the enunciation place allow to identify what Foucault defines as discursive formation ("complex set of relationships working as rules: Prescribe what in a discursive practice has needed to be related to refer to this or that object, to allow the presence of a specific statement, to use a specific set, to organize such strategy. Defining a system of formation in its individual singularity implies the characterization by the regularity of practice of a discourse or setting of statements"). The element that transforms a specific text into a discourse is the function of defining a certain enunciative identity, historically located, in the social space.

b. Subject (enunciator)

From this perspective there is another important consequence in somewhat of the subject implied. The origin of enunciation is not considered as a form of subjectivity but as a **place** where the enunciators are interchangeable. In Foucault's words, "describing a formulation from the view point of enunciation does not imply the analysis of relations between the author [*sic*] and what he says (or wanted to say, or said unconsciously), but the identification of what the **position** is that any individual must occupy to become the subject".

The subject assumes the status of enunciator that defines the discursive formation where s/he is located. Nevertheless, each discursive formation has not one enunciative position. Different sets of statements referring to the same position can be distributed on many discursive genres. The genre heterogeneity of a discursive formation contributes to define its identity.

There is a logical distinction between the speaker (locutor) - material source - and enunciator - textual author. The first one is an empirical reality and the second one a construction; s/he is the logical author and s/he is responsible for the text, but, simultaneously, s/he is constructed by it.

Enunciative locations imply the existence of certain institutions involved in the production and diffusion of specific discourses. Nevertheless, by the term "institution" just formal structures like, for example, the church, should not be understood. We should consider as institution any device that limits the production of enunciative functions, the status of enunciators and receivers, the acceptable content and the legitimate enunciative circumstances for such positioning.

c. "Materialization" of the text: the corpus

As the French School emphasizes, a corpus can be constructed from any discursive production; even if different practices stress different aspects. There is the possibility, considering the transmission support, of constructing any graphic or transcribed statement, although it is not graphically produced. They can be more or less context dependent; in other words, the statements can be directed to a subject present in the enunciative situation or to other subjects located in other contexts. The statements can also be imbedded in a specific structure: ritualized discourse requires a specific institutional context, with a strong thematic restriction, with much stability, etc.

In this description, therefore, transcribed interviews and conversations, written texts (articles, documents, . . .) and other textual material can be included.

SOME IMPLICATIONS FOR DISCOURSE ANALYSIS ANALYTICS

a. Discourse Analysis as practices

What is all this for?

We are no longer afraid to recognize that any scientific practice is influenced by social conditions where it happens - say the social, political or ideological context. If I have had a concern, this has been to adapt my political commitment with my professional activity.

This preoccupation was difficult to resolve within the scientific ideology in which I was instructed. I found a way when I first contacted Social Psychology or, specifically, Critical Social Psychology. Contact with Foucault's work was also emancipatory.

Discourses are social practices. If we follow Foucault, we should talk more about discursive practices than about discourses. Discursive practices are anonymous and historical rules which define the conditions for any enunciation for a specific period and for a specific community. Nevertheless, analysis is also a practice, not only to reveal or identify other discursive practices but also to transform them.

b. Context

By the historical character of the statement, any Discourse Analysis must consider the analysis of enunciation (the process of converting certain language into discourse). The enunciation is the imminent context of enunciation. The analysis of enunciation allows to relate language structures with social structures. At this point, we have an unanswered question: what is the role of linguistic analysis in discourse analysis?

ABOUT DISCOURSE AND SOCIAL STRUCTURE

I must recognize I consider discourse or discourse analysis important because its potential of connection with social structure. This is the last topic I would like to talk about.

Any practice, including discourse analysis, is drab if we accept a conception of social structure in only institutional/political or institutional/economic terms, or if we take any other reified version in which discursive, linguistic and meaningful aspects are external to social structure. This is because discourse

analysis would be incapable of social transformation. The specification of the support for what is exclusively an intention and a desire is important. I would be lying if I said I could sustain a clear and definite position.

To establish any relation between discourse and social structure is necessary to delimit, even provisionally, the notion of structure I am working with.

In an excellent paper by Douglas PORPORA, published on 1989 in the Journal for the Theory and Social Behavior after the controversy created by Jonathan TURNER (1988) about social structure, Porpora refers to at least four traditions in the notion of "social structure":

- As patterns of behavior grouped by periods (from Homans).
- As human relations systems between social positions (marxist).
- As regularities that govern social behavior (structural sociology).
- As collective rules that structure behavior (ethnomethodology, symbolic interactionism, etcetera).

No doubt we could talk about more traditions, even inside those four we have pointed out. Even if I look simplistic, I consider it appropriate at this point to "theatrically" assume a position that comprises all these topics: structure, social practice and discourse. This position is related to the last tradition, inspired by Giddens and Foucault, and has connections from Wittgenstein to, why not, certain marxists.

The initial approach could be more or less the following:

I think Giddens appropriately distinguishes between structure, system and structuring. **Structure** refers to the rules and/or the set of transformative relationships organized as properties of social systems. **System** refers to relations reproduced by actors or collectives organized as regular social practices. **Structuring** refers to the conditions that control the continuity or transmutation of structures and the reproduction of social systems.

It is not easy to locate discourse in this outline. It is easier to locate language if we use the concept of **agency**. It is indispensable, therefore, to accept the contributions I referred to above, in order to locate discourse adequately².

We should, in the first place, distinguish between **language** and **discourse**. As I consider discourse a form of social practice, discourse is a manifestation of language constrained by social structure (rules and/or sets of transformative relationships organized as properties of social systems).

² I am debfull with Fairclough's work

On the other hand, socially constructed orders constrain discourse. I understand as discursive orders sets of conventions associated with social institutions. Discursive orders, for example, are ideologically formed by power relations in social institutions and in society as a whole.

Because of the **duality of structure**, in Giddens's terms, discourse has effects on social structures and, simultaneously, the latter (structure) constrain the former (discourse); therefore, discourse contributes simultaneously to the maintenance and change of the social order.

Nevertheless, it is necessary to limit these concepts.

In the first place, that discourse is language as a social practice caused by social structures means that: Firstly, language is a part of and not something outside society; secondly, language is a social process; and, finally, language is a socially conditioned process (historically, we should add) in the same way as other non-linguistic processes. Actually, there is no external relationship "between" language and society but an internal one with structural duality. Language is a part of society; linguistic phenomena are social phenomena; and social phenomena are to a large degree linguistic phenomena.

The second limitation is more direct. To defend that social structure is a set of rules and relations does not mean to share the descriptive hypothesis of methodological situationism (it is possible to obtain adequate descriptive explanations for macro social phenomena from the analysis of micro social practices).

As different authors, like Knorr-Cetina, have pointed, we could oppose another hypothesis to this one: that macro-social order is, first, an order of representation. In other words, macro-social order is a sum of present references extracted from micro-situations.

Even if we could discuss this point, and we could consider this difference as trivial, the differentiation among discourse analysts, linguistic analysts and analysts of immediate interaction is important in our context. This difference allows the connection with constructionist positions.

EPILOGUE

This final assertive style does not obey a greater security in my position or the intention of being more provocative or persuasive. This style is a rhetorical device to reinforce my weak conviction.

I have proposed problems and projects for a solution. They result from consideration of the practices in which I have been involved and of presenting them in a rigorous academic context. If I have been involved, for example, in a highly problematic social situation, my questions have been directed more towards the consideration of the position I am occupying and how I could intervene, than which is the best way to study such a process. I inquired more about how to fight against the discourse of power than into whether the analysis procedure has been correct. The topic becomes dull if the analysis of a particular discourse is no more than an academic exercise.

Let me finish with a long quotation from Foucault:

"I am afraid you are mistaken twice: on the discursive practices I defined and on the part you reserve for human freedom. The positivity I have tried to establish must not be understood as a set of determinations imposed by the exterior on the individual's thought or as living in the interior and in advance. They better constitute the set of conditions by which a practice is established; producing partially or totally new statements by which they can be modified. This is more about the field in which the subject's initiative is articulated (without being its center) than about this initiative. This is about the rules used (without being invented or explicit); About the relations which support them (without being the last result nor their convergence point. This is about making explicit the discursive practices in its complexity thickness; About showing that talking is doing something, something different at expressing one's own thoughts, at translating one's own knowledge, at using language structures. This is about showing that adding a statement to a series of pre-existent statements is a complex and expensive act with certain conditions implicated (not only a situation, a context and certain motivations) and with certain rules (different from the logic and linguistic rules of construction). This is about showing that changing the discourse order does not mean 'new ideas', a new mentality through invention or creativity but some transformations in a practice; eventually in those who are coming and in their common articulation. I have not denied the possibility of changing discourse; I have removed the instant and exclusive right of subject sovereignty.